

Protocolized REDUction of non-resuscitation fluids versus usual care in SEptic shock patients- the REDUSE randomised clinical trial

Central data monitoring plan V1.0

Change history			
Version	Version date	Summary of changes	DOI
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Purpose

The purpose of the central data monitoring is to identify:

- 1) Centres with missing data
- 2) Centres with pre-defined quality deficiencies or noteworthy data deviations

The central data monitoring group will include Peter Bentzer, Jane Fisher, Janus C Jakobsen, Markus Harboe Olsen, and Maria Nelderup. The purpose of the central monitoring is not safety monitoring, as this is a task for the Data Safety and Monitoring Committee (DSMC).

Outcomes

Central data monitoring for missing data and noteworthy data deviations will be applied to primary and secondary outcome data in the trial. These outcomes are as follows:

Primary outcome

- All-cause mortality at 90 days

Secondary outcomes

- One or more complications in the ICU defined as one or more of the following events in the ICU:
 - a) Acute cerebral infarction (documented on MRI or CT scans of the brain) with corresponding neurological symptoms.
 - b) Acute coronary syndrome (defined as acute myocardial infarction or unstable angina pectoris) AND either reperfusion treatment (percutaneous coronary intervention, PCI or thrombolysis) or initiated/increased antithrombotic treatment.
 - c) Acute intestinal infarction (either diagnosed during surgery or by angiography).
 - d) Limb ischemia (defined as clinical signs of limb ischemia AND one of the following treatments: open or percutaneous vascular intervention, amputation, or initiation/increased antithrombotic treatment.
 - e) New onset severe acute kidney injury (defined as stage 3 according to the kidney disease improving global outcomes (KIDIGO) criteria).
- Days alive and free of mechanical ventilation within 90 days of inclusion.
- Cognitive function measured using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment BLIND test (MoCA-BLIND) at 6 months.
- Health-Related Quality of Life using the European Quality of Life visual analogue scale (EQ-VAS) at 6 months.

The primary outcome is based on data from a registry and the first two secondary outcomes are based on data from the patients' medical records and can be filled in at any time. The last two secondary outcomes are based on questionnaires administered to the participants by follow-up assessors and are therefore the most important variables to monitor for missing data.

Blinding

As some of the central data monitoring group members are part of the trial management and data analysis teams, we will keep these members blinded to the assigned intervention. To ensure blinding, a member of the central data monitoring group who is not a member of the analysis team will extract data from the eCRF.

For assessment of quality deficiencies and notable data deviations, the unblinded member of the team will extract a file which contains the site identity, outcome variables, and assigned intervention for each participant. None of the other central data monitoring group members will have access to this file. The data will be split into two files. The first file will contain only the site ID, assigned intervention (coded as A or B) and the fluid data. The second file will contain the participant ID, site ID and the other outcome variables with no fluid data. A script will be applied which will remove all patients from sites with fewer than 4 participants and will scramble the ID number and the order for the patients. As neither file will contain the study ID number, it will not be possible to link the assigned intervention to the other variables.

For assessment of missing data, the files that are extracted from the eCRF will contain the study ID but will not contain information about the assigned intervention, and therefore will be blinded.

Trial overview

We will present an overview of the trial at the time of the meeting, including the number of participants included, inclusion rate, and predicted amount of time required until trial completion.

Missing data

In this part, we will identify centres with missing data entries.

Form completeness

Data export file: enrolment list

The "enrolment list" report in the eCRF indicates the completion status of each form for each participant. This report will be exported from the eCRF for this analysis. Forms are due as follows:

Form	Due (from enrolment date)
Background	30 days
Origin of sepsis	30 days
Baseline	30 days
Discharge	90 days

Daily (one form per day in ICU up to 90 days)	120 days
Consent	120 days
90-day follow-up	120 days
6-month follow-up	7 months

The completion status will be “overdue” for any forms that are incomplete or not started after the due date listed above. Overall, the due dates are 30 days after the data would be obtained. For the daily forms, they will only be marked as complete when ALL required forms for that participant marked as complete. All participants with any overdue forms will be identified.

Follow-up completion

Data export file: 6-month follow-up

Because the 6-month follow-up form has a question about loss to follow-up, the form will be marked as complete also for participants for whom 6-month follow-up was not done. Therefore we will also identify participants who were lost to follow-up by examining the following variables:

Variable	Question text	Question type
FU180_WasCompleted	Was follow up completed	Yes/no
FU180_ReasonNotCompleted	If follow up not completed, give reason	Select one option: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient lost to follow up • Alive but refused to consent to follow up • Alive but unable to follow up for other reasons
FU180_ReasonNotCompletedOther	Specify	Free text

The number of participants per site with the variable “FU180_WasCompleted” marked as “no” will be determined. Sites with an excessive number of participants lost to follow-up will be identified and the reasons for loss to follow-up will be reviewed.

We will compile a list per site with the study ID for all participants with overdue forms, with active alerts, and with excessive levels of loss to follow-up.

Event forms completeness

Data: Patient alerts (filter for “SUSAC required” and “death form required”)

Certain forms in the CRF are only filled in or created when a certain event (death, protocol deviation, SUSAC) occurs. Completion of these forms is not indicated in the enrolment list, but instead will be monitored through patient alerts. When certain data are entered in the eCRF, an automatic alert is

raised which indicates that an additional form should be filled in. The “patient alerts” report in the eCRF shows all alerts raised, which indicate the form that should be filled in. The alert types and their corresponding required forms are indicated below:

Alert type	Required form
Death form required	Death
SUSAC required	SUSAC

The alert type filter in the report can be used to filter only for these alert types, and the active alerts filter can be used to show only alerts that have not been dismissed. The required forms will be checked manually to ensure that they have been filled in, and if so the alert will be dismissed. Any sites with active alerts left after this process will be identified.

Quality deficiencies

We will aim to identify centres with the following quality deficiencies:

- 1) Drift in the control group/Lack of separation in fluid volumes between groups
- 2) Proportion of randomized patients who are ineligible (randomized incorrectly)
- 3) Proportion of eligible patients not randomized in time (screening failures)

Lack of separation in fluid volumes between groups

Data export file: baseline, daily D0-5, daily D6-discharge, assigned intervention

To assess a potential lack of separation in fluid volumes, we will create graphs showing the total volume of all fluids, total volume of resuscitation fluids, and total volume of non-resuscitation fluids given per day in each intervention group. For each site, we will calculate mean and median differences between groups and 95% Hodges-Lehmann intervals. We will only use data from participants who have passed the deadline for completion of the daily forms to ensure data completeness. We will only assess separation at each site once complete data exists for at least 4 participants in each group.

The variables which will be used for the graph are:

Variable	Description
DD_FluidBalanceTotalThatDay	Total volume of fluids given that day (day 1-5)
DD_FluidBalanceResusFluids	Total volume of resuscitation fluids given that day (day 1-5)
DD_FluidBalanceNonResusFluids	Total volume of non-resuscitation fluids given that day (day 1-5)
DD_TotVolResusFluids	Total volume of resuscitation fluids given that day (day 6-discharge)
DD_TotVolNonResusFluids	Total volume of non-resuscitation fluids given that day (day 6-discharge)
BAS_FluidsIn_Crystalloids_RingersVol	Baseline Ringer's acetate/lactate - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_Crystalloids_NaClVol	Baseline 0.9% NaCl - volume

BAS_FluidsIn_Crystalloids_OtherVol	Baseline Other crystalloids - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_Colloids_Albumin4Vol	Baseline Albumin 4-5% - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_Colloids_Albumin20Vol	Baseline Albumin 20% - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_Colloids_OtherVol	Baseline Other colloids - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_BloodProducts_ErythrocytesVol	Baseline Erythrocytes - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_BloodProducts_PlasmaVol	Baseline Plasma - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_BloodProducts_PlateletsVol	Baseline Platelets - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_GlucoseAnyVol	Baseline Glucose (any concentration) - Volume
BAS_FluidsIn_ParenteralVol	Baseline Parenteral nutrition - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_EnteralNutritionVol	Baseline Enteral nutrition - volume
BAS_FluidsIn_EnteralWaterVol	Baseline Enteral water - volume

Proportion of randomized patients who are ineligible (randomized incorrectly)

Data export file: protocol deviations

To assess the number of ineligible patients who are randomized, a table will be created which shows the number of non-eligibility protocol violations per site.

The variables which will be used for the table are:

PD_NotEligible (yes/no)

PD_TreatmentNotReceived (yes/no)

Proportion of eligible patients not randomized in time (screening failures)

Data export file: patient eligibility

To assess the number of screening failures, a table will be created which shows the number of non-eligible patients with the reason "Screened more than 12 hours after ICU admission" per site.

From the "patient eligibility" export, the variables which will be used for the table are:

EL_OutcomeReason

Noteworthy data deviations

We will aim to identify centres with noteworthy data deviations, defined as:

- 1) outliers due to suspected random errors in data entries or insufficient validation ranges in the eCRF (suspected outliers)
- 2) suspected systematic errors in data entries due to misunderstandings (suspected misunderstandings)
- 3) potentially fabricated data (suspected fabrication of data)

Suspected outliers of the eCRF are defined as outlying observations for continuous data points in the monitoring data report, identified by visual inspection. If such a data entry was identified in the data monitoring report, it would be marked as a suspected outlier.

Suspected misunderstandings are defined as any unexpected differences in the distribution of data among centres that may represent differences in coding practice, misinterpretation of the eCRF, or overall study design. An example of this could be a local misunderstanding of the definition of a trial outcome, e.g. diagnosing the outcome by different criteria than described in the study protocol. In such a situation, we would expect an abnormally high or low frequency of the event for binary data, or a shift/abnormally large variability in the data distribution for a continuous outcome, in the centre where the misunderstanding occurred.

Suspected fabrication of data is defined as an unexpected distribution or variance in data at each centre that may represent fabricated data. For continuous data, we would expect to see a different shape or distribution of data when visualized graphically, since natural variance is difficult to fabricate. An example of this could be an unexpectedly narrow or wide distribution of a continuous variable at a particular centre. An unexpectedly large or small prevalence of a binary data point can be a sign of data fabrication or due to a misunderstanding (see suspected misunderstandings above).

Assessment

Continuous variables

Data export file: 90-day follow-up, 6-month follow-up

We will create box plots showing the median, range, and individual values for each of the following variables per site:

- 1) Days alive and free of mechanical ventilation (FU90_MechanicalVent)
- 2) MOCA score calculated as the sum of the following variables:
 - FU180_MoCAMemory
 - FU180_MoCAAttentionDigits
 - FU180_MoCAAttentionLetters
 - FU180_MoCAAttentionSubtraction
 - FU180_MoCALangRepeat
 - FU180_MoCALangFluency
 - FU180_MoCAAbstraction
 - FU180_MoCADelayedRecall
 - FU180_MoCAOrientation
 - FU180_HighestEducation (+1 score only if No formal education, Incomplete primary/lower secondary school, Complete primary/lower secondary school, Incomplete upper secondary school, or Complete upper secondary school; +0 score if Some university-level education, without degree OR University-level education, with degree – may differ for sites in different countries)
- 3) EQ-5D-5L Visual analog scale (FU180_EQVASHealthToday)

Binary variables

Data export file: 90-day follow-up, Daily D0-5, Daily D6-discharge

We will create a table showing the percentage of participants at each site with a positive answer to each of the following variables at any time during ICU stay:

Outcome	Variable	Positive answer
Mortality at 90 days	FU90_Status	yes
Acute cerebral infarction	DD_ComplicationsIschemicCerebral	yes
Acute coronary syndrome	DD_ComplicationsIschemicHeart	yes
Acute intestinal infarction	DD_ComplicationsIschemicIntestine	yes
Limb ischemia	DD_ComplicationsIschemicLimb	yes
New onset severe acute kidney injury (only counts the first time a positive answer is achieved even if it continues to be positive over several days)	DD_ComplicationsAKI_KDIGO OR DD_RenalHighestCreatinine OR DD_RenalReplacementTherapy	Stage 3 >353.6 umol/L Yes, but only if all previous days (including baseline BAS_RenalRRT) are no

Monitoring of quality deficiencies and noteworthy data deviations will start after the first 100 participants have been randomised. At this first meeting, the workflow will be reviewed and revised if needed, and the frequency of future meetings will be determined.

A data report for quality deficiencies and noteworthy data deviations will be generated automatically after extraction of the above specified data from the eCRF. We will only include data from centres with more than 5 included participants, and for every variable a minimum of five participants must be added to be presented. This is to ensure some degree of anonymisation and because data assessment is difficult in very small samples. The report will be blinded to the identity of the centres by assigning them a new name in the report, based on a seed generated by the absolute time of the computer.

The data report will be assessed and the results will be logged in a central monitoring log by the central data monitoring group.

Corrective actions

Corrective actions for missing data

The data on missing data entries described above will be extracted regularly from the eCRF. Data form completion will be calculated by dividing the number of incomplete forms of each type by the number of forms expected to be completed (i.e. the number of randomized participants for whom the form due date has passed).

The percentage of incomplete forms will be reported for each centre in a data completion report (**Appendix 2**). The report will be assessed and approved by the central data monitoring group.

Following approval, the report will be circulated to all investigators. The identified study IDs for participants with missing data will not be included in the report.

The trial manager will contact investigators from centres with missing data and inform them of the study IDs of participants with missing data, including the specific data forms affected. As there will be zero tolerance to missing data entries, the investigators will be requested to fill-out the missing data entries as soon as possible.

At the first meeting, the workflow will be reviewed and revised if needed, and the frequency of future meetings will be determined.

Corrective actions for quality deficiencies and noteworthy data deviations

If a centre is found to have a high number or proportion of the prespecified quality deficiencies, this will be reported in the central monitoring log according to the template in **Appendix 3**. The site principal investigator will be contacted for an elaboration and to discuss how to improve, which will also be recorded in the log.

For noteworthy data deviations, every variable will be assessed by the central monitoring group via the following steps:

1. Is there a centre with noteworthy data as per the previous definitions? [Yes] / [No]
2. If yes, which suspicion has been raised? [Describe]
3. Will any course of action be taken? [Yes] / [No]
4. If yes, the trial manager will contact the principal investigator and take the relevant course of action
5. Results of the course of action will be noted

All decisions, including course of action, will be reported in the central monitoring log according to the template in **appendix 4**.

Final report

Once the central monitoring log has been approved and a summary has been written, a conversion key will be sent to the trial manager for re-identification of centres and to contact relevant principal investigators. Once the trial manager has been in touch with all relevant investigators, the report will be revised, and the central monitoring log will be updated as needed.

A short version of the final report will be uploaded to the trial webpage (reduse-trial.com).

Appendices

Appendix 1: Step-by-step overview of the central monitoring process

1. Missing data identification, reporting and contact to principal site investigators
2. Quality deficiencies identification, reporting and decision on contacting principal site investigators
3. Noteworthy data deviation identification, reporting and decision on contacting principal site investigators.

These steps may not occur at each meeting. The frequency with which each of these steps will be carried out will be decided after the first meeting and may be amended subsequently as needed.

Appendix 2: Data completion report template

Site	Daily forms incomplete (%)	90-day follow-up form incomplete (%)	6-month follow-up form incomplete (%)	6-month follow-up not done	Number of unresolved alerts

Appendix 3: Quality deficiency assessment log template

Quality deficiency	Blinded site ID	Comment	Will any action be taken? (yes/no)	Unblinded site ID	Summary of action taken

Appendix 4: Noteworthy data deviation assessment log template

Variable	Blinded site ID	Suspicion raised (suspected outlier, misunderstanding, or fabrication)	Will any action be taken? (yes/no)	Unblinded site ID	Summary of action taken